

EXTENSION OF TISSS TEST METHODOLOGY FROM CHIP LEVEL TO BOARD LEVEL FOR IMPROVED TRANSPORTABILITY AND DECREASED LIFE-CYCLE COSTS

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Abstract

This paper will discuss an implementation of a set of tools designed to improve the supportability and transportability of board level Test Program Sets (TPS) to multiple test environments. The Tester Independent Support Software System (TISSS) was tried and proven sufficient to test Advanced Tactical Fighter (ATF) complex digital Line Replaceable Modules (LRM). The proposed methodology is an extension of the (TISSS) philosophy for component level testing in which Computer Aided Design (CAD) designer data is extracted, formatted into generic Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers (IEEE) standard formats, translated and postprocessed into tester specific TPSs. This new TPS re-host method will use tools derived from TISSS, Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) packages, and will be supplemented by some Rome Laboratory customized software tools. The aim of this effort is to demonstrate to the depot maintenance repair community a better approach to TPS development and re-hosting versus conventional methods in terms of reduced costs, time and improved efficiency.

Introduction

This paper is based on a new TPS re-hosting approach currently going on at The San Antonio Air Logistics Center, Advanced Diagnostics Technology Insertion Center (ADTIC). The ADTIC is chartered under the Advanced Computer Resources and Electronics Technology Area (ACRETA), PAD 86-MM*-601(1) to prototype Advanced Technology Test Equipment. This TPS re-host prototype is an extension of the ACRETA PAD to examine new technologies and methodologies to reduce Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) proliferation and support costs. The first TPS re-host prototype is a C-5A aircraft Input/Output (I/OC) Controller Shop Replaceable Unit (SRU). The second TPS is a development effort for

a 256K Random Access Memory (RAM) SRU located in the Depot Automatic Test System for Avionics (DATSA) test station. For both SRUs, the targeted TPS re-host testers are the GenRad 275X and an Air Force ATLAS language based unit. The main intent of the paper is to illustrate one re-host effort of the I/OC SRU to the GenRAD 275X environment

Each Unit Under Test (UUT) will be tested down to the component level. The fault detection and localization capability will be provided by the ATE simulators. Although the proposed new methodology will add one more step to the overall test process, it is essential to achieve the significant rewards listed below:

- 1) Lower cost method for re-hosting multiple TPSs to new tester environments
- 2) UUT tester independence
- 3) Increased UUT and tester availability
- 4) Decreased life-cycle cost for UUT supportability
- 5) Generic/non-proprietary format for describing and transporting SRU models, stimulus and expected response information readily to multiple simulation and tester environments.

Background

There are some inherent problems with conventional TPS development methods:

- 1) Test specifications are not always complete and accurate, and must be interpreted by test engineers
- 2) Difficult to convey the testing intent from the design engineer to the test engineer
- 3) Without the designer's input or test philosophy, a test engineer has difficulty discerning what tests are important and tests are not
- 4) Test engineers are usually unaware of the rationale behind component values, component types, connectivity; i.e. what criteria is important for a

complete test.

The life-cycle cost (i.e. 15 to 20 years) for DOD unique test equipment is usually more expensive to maintain compared to COTS testers due to the limited quantities and uniqueness of the tester resources and software. As these testers age, it becomes cost prohibitive and even impossible to continue to repair them. At this point, the Air Force is faced with the difficult choice of reverse engineering the tester or replacing it.

If the decision to acquire a new tester is made, then the TPSs from the old tester must be re-hosted to run on the new tester. The cost of the hardware is just a fraction of the cost to re-host TPSs. DOD maintenance shops/depots need to reduce TPS development and re-host costs and provide sufficient fault detection and isolation down to the component level. Air Force Depots require faster, more efficient and effective methods for developing and re-hosting Shop Replaceable Units (SRUs) TPSs. By using concurrent engineering techniques, these problems can be resolved in one integrated approach.

These problems increase the complexity of TPS development, as well as increasing the overall cost of manpower and re-hosting and software and hardware maintenance. These problems highlight an important point which is the necessity for the Department Of Defense (DOD) maintenance depots to develop new methodologies for TPS re-hosting. The focus of this paper is to propose one such method for TPS re-hosting.

Approach

The TISSS effort proved to be an effective methodology for developing and re-hosting TPS for microelectronic components. The main difference between chip versus board testing is that board level testing requires the TPS to identify each faulty component. A typical test for a chip includes applying stimulus vectors to the edge connector and compares the device-under-test's actual response to the expected response (i.e. Go/NoGo). If the actual response is exactly the same as the expected response then the device under test is considered good, otherwise the device is defective and discarded.

The board Go/NoGo test represents a very small part of the test program. The bulk of the test program development effort for a board is consumed in the development of diagnostic routines to identify the faulty component. A complete test program for a board must contain a diagnostic routine for each test that fails. Ideally, the diagnostic routine will identify the faulty component. It is not always possible or feasible to identify the exact faulty component or

components, instead the fault is localized to a small group of components called the *ambiguity group*.

There are two methodologies for developing fault isolation routines. The test engineer may manually write each diagnostic and guided probe routine for each failure mode. This method is expensive and takes a longer time to develop than the other method. Manually written test programs are only developed when other methods are not possible such as mixed analog and digital circuitry. The second approach is to use ATE simulators (i.e. GenRad Inc.'s HiLo, Teradyne Inc.'s LASAR, or the Navy's Hierarchal Integrated Test System (HITS) which automatically produce a fault dictionary and guided probe information.

Adherence to sound engineering principles allows the test engineer to speculate that the SRU VHDL Hardware Description Language (VHDL) structural model is a software model replica of the physical SRU. Furthermore, this holds true for the Waveform And Vector Exchange Specification (WAVES) data set representing the complete set of stimulus and response vectors required to simulate complete SRU functionality. Taking this information into account, our project of developing/re-hosting the test programs is a straight forward process with the porting of the VHDL models and test vectors into the ATE simulator environment. The VHDL models, and in particular, the stimulus and response vectors will be validated in the design environment. Once the design vectors are ported into the test environment, the test engineer will have an improved confidence of the test vectors integrity. This will give the test engineer a running start in the ATE simulator environment, as compared to conventional methods of test vector generation from scratch.

Process

The RAM and I/OC TPSs re-host to just one specific tester environment (i.e. GenRad 275X) is the basis for this portion of the paper. The process will describe the major stages entailed in this effort. The major steps are summarized below:

1) Generation of Test Requirements Documentation - The first step for re-hosting a TPS is to obtain Test Requirements (TR) from the UUT manufacture, or to generate them if unavailable. The test engineer interprets how the board functions, determines tester resources required, generates UUT block diagrams, and may develop a UUT flow diagram. For the 256K RAM and I/OC UUTs, the TRs are not available.

To reduce future TPS re-host costs and time, it is advantageous for the test data to be

interchangeable between test environments. ¹Test Requirements File format (TRF) is a new requirements definition approach to specify the desired values and tests. The product specifications are converted by describing what is to be tested, and how it is to be tested. Rome Laboratory (RL) originally developed TRF to generate micro-circuit specifications. Our project is extending TRF's capabilities to document board level specifications for both SRUs.

2) Generation of Simulation Vectors - If the stimulus test vectors are not available from the manufacture, they must be created either by manual techniques (i.e. Figure 1) or by employing a COTS software tool to generate the stimulus and response test vectors from a portion of the existing Test Program (TP).

3) Creation of VHDL Model - The generic process for developing a Circuit Card Assembly (CCA) structural VHDL model is relatively straight forward. The board modeling process begins with its schematic. All circuit nodes are identified with a unique identification (i.e. acronym) and correct fanout. The next step, developing port maps for the VHDL model, is accomplished by writing a simple database program to organize the components by IC number, part number, I/O pin assignment and associated signal name. When data entry is completed, the DATABASE tool is directed to generate an ASCII file which can be simply edited into component port maps and integrated into the structure model of the board.

The CCA model is then ready for compilation and simulation. During compilation of the 256K RAM SRU, the board model accesses the Transistor Transistor Logic (TTL) source model library developed by a COTS VHDL models vendor. This library contained all of the Small Scale Integration (SSI) TTL components with the exception of two components (i.e. Intel 8203 controller and 2164 dynamic RAM). The models for these two ICs were created semi-automatically using a COTS software tool. A powerful feature of this tool is that with minimal designer input of some simple algorithms, the COTS tool will develop the UUT test bench and the necessary stimulus and response test vectors. These elements are essential in the UUT model simulation and validation process.

4) Simulation - The 1076 Std VHDL structural model of the UUT is simulated in a selected VHDL simulator environment validating the test engineer's stimulus/response test vectors and model's completeness. Corrections to the models and/or test vectors are annotated and re-simulated. This step

validates the VHDL structural model and the test vectors (Figure 1).

5) Convert VHDL to ATE Simulator Netlist Format - The input to most ATE simulators is a netlist description representing the schematic of the UUT. This same information is available in the VHDL structural model. A conversion utility will convert the VHDL structural model to the netlist format of the target ATE simulator. Figure 3 illustrates the similarity of the netlist for the GenRad 275X ATE simulator and a VHDL structural model. Component models that exist in the ATE simulator library will not be converted from VHDL. VHDL models not available in the ATE simulator will be developed.

6) Validated Test Vectors Converted to WAVES - ²WAVES, IEEE standard 1029.1-1991, is a language for capturing and exchanging stimulus and expected response information (test vectors/signal histories) for digital microelectronics and CCAs. WAVES represents the test stimulus and response information in a standard, non-proprietary, format that can be quickly transported among multiple simulation and tester platforms. WAVES fits into concurrent engineering techniques by representing all levels of digital waveforms and test vectors.

Design engineers create the validated test vectors and timing information required to validate the full functioning digital design. ³Our WAVES data set constitutes six files with file extensions of .HEADER, .LOGIC, .FRAMES, .GENERATOR, .DUT, and .PATTERN (Figure 1).

After stripping out the response test vectors, the WAVES data set is ready to be ported into the targeted tester's simulation environment. The validated stimulus vectors will reduce the time required to create the response test vectors in the tester environment by providing the test engineer an improved confidence for the stimulus vector's integrity.

7) TP Generation Inside the ATE Environment - The main components of a TPS consists of an ATE Test Program (TP), Technical Order (T.O.) document and an Interface Test Adapter (ITA). The test program is a set of instructions that execute various tests on a UUT. The T.O. contains necessary written information and instructions on how to connect the UUT to the ITA and the ITA to the ATE Interface Connector Adapter (ICA), how to test the UUT and what UUT components will be tested. The ITA can contain either passive or active components. If the TP and ATE are capable of providing adequate stimulus, then the ITAs will tend to be passive.

The RAM TPS re-host effort to the GenRad 275X tester environment will be the example used to describe the TPS re-host inside the ATE environment. Described below are the major stages entailed in this effort (Figure 2).

8) CONVERT WAVES DATA SET TO ATE SIMULATOR FORMAT - Test engineer uses a software tool to convert WAVES stimulus test vectors into the accepted format for the targeted ATE simulator environment. The stimulus test vectors exercise the UUT. The simulator's response can then be validated against the response vectors in the WAVES data set.

9) INTERFACE TEST ADAPTER CREATED - Interface Test Adapter (ITA) is designed based on the UUT's edge connectors, test points, ATE Interface Connector Assembly (ICA) pin map, power/stimulus/response requirements and special UUT requirements.

10) ATE SIMULATION - In the GenRad 275X's simulator environment, the test engineer invokes the ATE simulator which simulates the UUT with provided stimulus test vectors. The simulator outputs various files which make the core of the UUT executable Test Program (TP). These files include the probe database and fault dictionary. The ATE's stimulus and response test vectors are inherent in the TP. As the ATE simulator simulates the UUT, the stimulus test vectors are generated on-the-fly. The TP is practically complete at this point if the target ATE is the same as the ATE simulator (i.e. HiLo to GenRad Inc., LASAR to Teradyne Inc., etc.). To target an ATE that is different than the simulator used would require a post processor. Various post processors are currently available in industry. If the fault statistics do not demonstrate the minimal acceptable fault coverage (i.e. usually greater than 95%), the test engineer will determine if it is necessary to modify the TP to achieve the desired fault coverage. When sufficient fault coverage has been achieved to satisfy the test requirements, the test engineer can then proceed to the actual tester environment.

11) TEST VERIFICATION - For the GenRad 275X environment, the test engineer installs a "good" UUT and applies standard TPS verification procedures such as node verification and fault insertion. These utilities verify the simulation exactly duplicates the actual UUT. This is performed by comparing the simulated values of each node with actual values of the "good" UUT. A manual iterative process is performed on each node not accessible at the edge connector. If a node discrepancy occurs, then the test engineer makes modifications to the

simulator models until 100% node verification is achieved. If the minimum acceptable fault coverage is not or cannot be achieved through the ATE simulator, then the test engineer determines if user define tests should be hard coded to increase the overall fault coverage. At this point, the TPS is complete with the exception of documentation and T.O. verification.

Conclusion

Short and long term benefits will be realized by more efficient and effective sharing of design and test information through the use of compatible and standard electronic data formats. ⁴We estimate that overall test development time can be reduced by as much as 60% by porting of the design environment's stimulus and response vectors into the test environment. The ADTIC's effort demonstrates the viability of using available conventional technology and generic standards to accomplish the task of re-hosting TPSs from one environment to another. This process does not require the development of any new standards and makes efficient use of existing standards as well as commercial tools and technology. ⁵Efficient TPS re-hosting enables maintenance depots to select a test strategy to obtain adequate testing for the best price.

There is a negative side to this approach. While transferring raw test vectors with timing information will definitely reduce TPS re-host/development costs, there may be a reduction in the useability and efficiency of the ATE's capabilities. For instance, the raw stimulus test vectors may represent an algorithm that the ATE environment may handle very efficiently with its built-in capabilities. A good example is the "walking ones" routine for RAM testing. Test environments vary greatly in this area, it would depend on a case by case basis. This new testing approach will hopefully pave the way for acceptance and development of commercial software tools to convert CAE models and stimulus and response test vectors into targeted ATE simulator environments.

Future Work and Initiatives

As mentioned in the Introduction, the second effort will consist of re-hosting a TPS, for each SRU, to an Air Force inventory ATLAS language based tester. This TPS re-host effort will be much the

Figure 1. Generation of Stimulus and Response Vectors

Figure 2. Tester Specific (i.e. GenRad 275X) Environment

ATE Simulator Environment

VHDL Code

CIRCUIT UUT

P1,
P2,
P3,
P4);

74LS74 U1
(1=P3
2= U1P2,
.
.
.
13=U21P5);
.
.
.

input P1;
output P2;
input P3;
bidir P4;

ENDCIRCUIT

entity of UUT is
port map(P1: in,
 P2: out,
 P3: in,
 P4: inout);
end UUT;

architecture structure of UUT is
-- COMPONENT DECLARATIONS
component 74LS74 is
port map
 (CLR1,D1,CLK1,PR1,Q1,QB1,
 QB2,Q2,PR2,CLK2,D2,CLR2);

-- INTERNAL SIGNAL DECLARATIONS
signal U1P1,U2P7, ...,U21P5;

begin

 U1: 74LS74
 port map(CLR1=P3,
 D1=U1P2,
 .
 .
 .
 CLR2=U21P5);
 .
 .
 .
end structure;

Figure 3. ATE Simulator Input Verses VHDL Code

same as the one for the GenRad 275X environment. A conversion utility will convert the VHDL models into HITS models not available in the HITS library. Again utilizing a conversion software tool, the WAVES test vectors will be converted into HITS's input format to postprocess an executable TPS to an ATLAS language based tester. The fault dictionary and probe database will be generated. The postprocessed TPS will be executed on a "good" UUT to verify the UUT fault coverage. If the resultant fault coverage is not acceptable, the HITS's models and test vectors will need to be modified. In addition, this may result in a change to the VHDL models and WAVES test vectors.

The ADTIC will continue to monitor IEEE initiatives and industry trends to identify new approaches for TPS re-hosting in the depot maintenance environment.

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References

1. W.H. Debany, N.A. Koziarz, and J.M. Nagy, "Converting Test Requirements into Test Programs Sets," Draft, IEEE AUTOTESTCON, 1993.
2. J.P. Hanna and W.J. Horth, "A New Methodology For Test Program Set generation and Re-Hosting," Proc. IEEE AUTOTESTCON, 1991.
3. R.G. Hillman, "WAVES: A Simulation and Tester View," Proc. IEEE AUTOTESTCON, pp. 279-285, 1990.
4. D. Romanchik, "Simulating Tester Resources," Test & Measurement World, pp. 71-72, Dec. 1992.
5. S.F. Scheiber, "Evaluating Test-Strategy Alternatives," Test & Measurement World, Apr. 1992.